

Performance-Based Design Procedure of a Novel Friction-Based Cladding Connection for Blast Mitigation

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Abstract

Cladding systems are conventionally designed to provide buildings with environmental protection against wind, temperature, humidity, moisture, etc. Recently, researchers have proposed to leverage these systems to provide additional protection against manmade (e.g., blast) and natural (e.g., earthquakes, hurricanes) hazards. This can be achieved, for example, by redesigning the connection between the cladding and the structural system to provide energy dissipation via friction. While promising, the use of flexible cladding connection has only been considered for singular hazards. In this study, the authors propose a novel semi-active damping system to connect the cladding to the structure via a variable friction mechanism. By varying the normal force applied on friction plates through a system of adjustable toggles, it is possible to mitigate vibrations over a wide frequency range, therefore enabling mitigation of different types of hazards (i.e. to achieve multi-hazard resistance). In its passive in-situ mode, the device is designed to provide very high stiffness and friction resistance to mitigate the effects of blast.

The objective of this paper is to enable a holistic integration of said device within the structural design process by developing a performance-based design procedure. The study will focus on the passive in-situ mode of the device, which will provide a stepping stone for the development of performance-based design procedures for its semi-active (i.e. actuated) capabilities. The proposed performance-based design procedure consists of the following: 1) determine the design performance criteria, including the blast properties and allowable connection gap between the cladding and structure; 2) select design properties for the cladding connection, including stiffness and damping; and 3) design a rubber impact bumper located between the structure and the cladding in order to mitigate slamming of the cladding into the structure for very high blast loads.

Keywords: Semi-active damping, high performance control systems, variable friction, cladding, structural control, blast mitigation, performance-based design.

1. Introduction

Civil infrastructures, including buildings and energy, lifeline, communication, and transportation systems, provide significant services and benefits to our communities. These systems need to be designed, constructed, and maintained to sufficiently resist the effects of service and extreme loads so that their continuous daily operability and public safety can be sustained. In particular, modern construction techniques and materials enable the construction of lighter and more flexible structures - as an example, increasing wind-induced vibrations which may create discomfort to occupants and result in frequent inoperability of that structure. Also, recent extreme events (e.g., earthquakes, hurricanes, tornadoes, storm surges, accidental and intentional blasts) have illustrated the vulnerabilities of buildings and transportation infrastructures to sudden losses in functionality.

A solution to increase structural performance to extreme loads in particular is a performance-based design (PBD) approach [1]. For dynamic loads, the strategy is to appropriately size structural stiffness, damping, and inertia such that the resulting response meets a prescribed performance level. For wind and seismic loads, the targeted response can often be achieved via the implementation of supplemental damping systems [2]. In cases when multiple excitation inputs are considered individually or as a combination (i.e. multi-hazard excitations), a PBD approach becomes difficult to implement with a passive supplemental damping strategy.

It is possible to leverage cladding systems for mitigation of different hazards. Cladding serves both as the point of application of externally applied lateral loads such as wind and blast as well as a contributor of inertial force via the excitation of its mass due to seismic or wind-induced vibrations. As designed in current practice, the cladding is mounted to the structure via tie-back connections, commonly comprised of angles bolted to embeds in the floor slab diaphragm and cladding panel. Since conventional connections are very stiff, the cladding will typically not be an active participant in resisting seismic and wind loads. The cladding is typically designed to suffer some permanent deformations and damage yet not experience blowout when subjected to blast loading, but the cladding elements may transfer significant reactions to the structure, thus requiring the cladding-to-structure connections to be strengthened. Rigid support of the cladding will not provide energy dissipation for intense but short-duration blast loads, thereby ensuring that both the cladding and the building itself will undergo a maximum response to the load.

Passive cladding connections have been previously proposed for dissipating energy from earthquake excitation. In these systems, the cladding is utilized as a mass damper which helps mitigate inertial loading due to seismic vibration rather than merely contributing to those loads as an added mass source. Early work by others [3, 4] examined ductile connections and demonstrated their ability to reduce interstory floor drifts. More recently Maneetes and Mermari [5] proposed a passive friction damper that is designed to slip when subjected to moderate to high intensity earthquakes. Baird *et al.* [6] proposed a U-shaped flexural

35 plate connection to dissipate earthquake energy. Previous research has also considered on passive energy
36 dissipation for blast loads. A significant amount of early research has focused on the use of sacrificial systems
37 composed of foam-based materials that are placed in locations that experience bearing during a blast event
38 [7, 8]. Though effective under certain blast conditions, these materials offer little potential for resisting mul-
39 tiple hazards since they are not capable of dissipating energy for lower frequency loading. Few studies have
40 been performed to explore the use of damping devices rather than sacrificial crushing materials or devices
41 for blast applications. Among these studies are those by Amadio and Bedon [9] [10], who have recently
42 investigated the use of viscoelastic dampers at the lateral connection of blast-resistant curtain wall systems
43 to the structure. The results of these studies have shown that the viscoelastic dampers provide significant
44 reductions in the peak response of the curtain wall systems that were considered [9]. These reductions enable
45 both a lighter design of the curtain wall to meet the same level of blast resistance and a reduction of the
46 reactions transmitted to the structural system.

47 All of these examples of energy dissipation connectors are passive systems, whose mitigation capabilities
48 are limited over a relatively narrow performance bandwidth [11, 12, 13], and are therefore limited to mitigat-
49 ing single specific types of hazards. Alternatively, semi-active, hybrid, and active structural control solutions
50 can be used to tailor the performance of connection devices to a wider spectrum of loading demands and
51 frequencies. These high-performance control systems (HPCS) can perform over a wide excitation bandwidth
52 and are ideal for multi-hazard applications. Several examples of devices enabling HPCS are provided in the
53 referenced literature[14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19] .

54 In this paper, the authors propose to a novel semi-active connector for cladding systems to provide
55 multi-hazard mitigation. The device is based on a variable friction mechanism which is placed at the lateral
56 connection interface between the cladding and the floor slab diaphragm. Semi-actively controlled friction
57 has gained popularity due to its high energy dissipation and low power requirement. The friction force is
58 generated by contact plates with specifically selected materials and controlled by an actuator, which can
59 apply a varying normal force to the plates via adjustable toggles. Typical actuator types used in generating
60 the normal force include pneumatic [20, 21], hydraulic [22], electro-magnetic [23, 24], electro-mechanical [25]
61 and piezoelectric [26, 27, 28, 29] devices. Examples of large-scale variable friction devices include 25 kN
62 [30, 31] and 45 kN [32] capacity systems.

63 The friction plates can be unlocked and actuated via the semi-active control algorithm to provide variable
64 friction force for wind and earthquake hazard mitigation. However, the proposed semi-active connection is
65 designed to be in a passive in-situ configuration (at which the actuator is locked and the resulting friction is
66 constant) during daily operations. This configuration is engineered for blast resistance because blast loading,
67 whether from an accidental or intentional explosion, is difficult to predict and occurs too suddenly for a semi-
68 active control algorithm to respond. Given the novelty of the semi-active connection, PBD procedures need

69 to be developed to facilitate the holistic integration of these devices into the structural design. This paper
 70 focuses on the design of the device in its passive in-situ configuration to maintain daily operations and
 71 withstand unpredictable blast events.

72 2. Semi-Active Connection

Figure 1: Semi-active device integrated in (a) floor slab (top view); and (b) building façade (elevation view).

73 The proposed connection is a novel semi-active friction device which provides a lateral connection between
 74 the cladding and the floor diaphragm of the buildings structural system. The device, schematized in Fig.
 75 1 (a), consists of sliding friction plates subjected to a normal force produced by an actuator applied via a
 76 toggle system. The device is inset into prefabricated box-out in the floor slab in order to provide a high
 77 degree of mechanical restraint. The device is set into the box-out, which consists of steel plates that are
 78 anchored into the slab via metal studs, with its friction plates oriented vertically (thus pushing outward
 79 against the high stiffness provided by the slab). The inner plates of the device extend outward to connect to
 80 the interior face of the cladding. A rubber impact bumper is integrated between the interface of the cladding
 81 and the slab edge (Fig. 1 (a)) in order to mitigate slamming of the cladding into the structure. The device
 82 is designed to provide equivalent damping due to friction hysteresis based on a decentralized scheme, where
 83 each cladding panel (Fig. 1 (b)) is damped individually between each floor. Other configurations can be
 84 used to accommodate construction preferences, cladding types, and load demands. For example, only the
 85 bottom connections to the cladding could be semi-active, while the top connections could be conventional
 86 gravity hanger connections.

Figure 2: Schematic of the semi-active device mechanism: (a) unlocked mode; and (b) locked mode.

The force diagram of the proposed connection is illustrated in Fig. 2. The actuator generates a controllable force f_a to push or pull the toggles. Changes in the toggles' geometry provide the variation in the friction force f_t , resulting in a variable normal pressure σ_p on the friction plates. The device can be used in three different damping configurations:

1. Toggles are locked for daily operations (Fig. 2 (a)). Both toggles are pushed vertically and provide the maximum normal pressure σ_p on the friction plates, thus locking of the device in a high friction mode. This is the passive in-situ mode, because no power is required to maintain the toggles in the locked position. The actuator remains in its position and acts as a stiff element. This high state of friction is sufficient to avoid slippage of the connection during low-to-moderate loading, during which the cladding system performs similar to any conventional cladding system with "rigid" connections to the structure. The passive mode will also be designed for blast load mitigation such that the blast-induced reactions from the cladding panel will be higher than the connections static friction, resulting in slippage of the connection and energy dissipation. No feedback control is required during blast.
2. Toggles are unlocked and allow variable friction via the actuator. The normal pressure σ_p is varied by the actuator force f_a and the device behaves as a semi-active friction damper. This particular configuration can be used to control interstory drift to limit damage to cladding (e.g. under extreme wind or seismic events).
3. Toggles are disconnected. The friction plates are fully disengaged and the resistance provided by the connection is minimal, resulting in near-zero axial force f_t and normal pressure σ_p . This configuration is also passive, as no power input is necessary once the toggles are retracted. This configuration can be used to limit acceleration transfer to floors as well as to reset the connections to their initial state following their response to an extreme event.

In what follows, PBD procedures are developed for configuration 1 (toggles locked for daily operations). While the proposed mitigation device is very specific, such PBD procedures could be modified and/or applied

111 to any passive device based on friction and impact rubber mechanisms used in dissipating blast loads.
112 Representative models of the device performance based on current prototypes will be used to demonstrate
113 the PBD procedure. Note that the fabrication and characterization of a prototype is part of a current
114 investigation and is out-of-the-scope of this paper. The re-positioning of the device and cladding is also
115 left to future work; because a manual reset could be impractical, one would need to engineer a mechanism
116 enabling automatic reset, termed self-centering mechanism.

117 3. Methodology

118 The dynamics of the structure-cladding interaction under blast loading is nonlinear given the presence of
119 a friction element and an impact bumper (nonlinear stiffness) in combination with the high peak and rapid
120 time decay of a blast load. Some simplifications are made in order to facilitate the derivation of analytical
121 solutions, which will be used to estimate transfer functions that utilize PBD. The analytical solutions will be
122 derived for the first half-cycle displacement response of the cladding following a blast load, which corresponds
123 to the maximum displacement of the cladding and highest possible impact force on the building. This section
124 discusses the simplified models used for the derivation of these solutions. These solutions are then compared
125 with computational models to verify the applicability of the analytical simplifications.

126 3.1. Structure-cladding model

127 The structure-cladding interaction is studied both in a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) and a two degree-
128 of-freedom (2DOF) configuration. The SDOF configuration is utilized to derive analytical solutions for PBD
129 procedures. In this model, the structure is fixed based on the assumption that the dynamics of the structure
130 itself can be negligible during the first half-cycle of the claddings displacement. This assumption is often
131 used in the simulation of cladding components when subjected to short duration blast loads [33, 34, 35, 36].
132 Fig. 3 (a) shows the SDOF representation of the cladding and its connection. The cladding of mass m_c is
133 connected to the structure via a stiffness element k_c and a viscous element c_c , and a friction element f_c . The
134 friction element f_c represent the friction force from proposed semi-active device and k_c and c_c stands for the
135 total stiffness and damping properties of cladding system including the gravity connection and non-friction
136 components of proposed device. An impact rubber of length l_r is installed at a distance l_c from the structure.
137 The rubber is modeled as a nonlinear stiffness element k_r and viscous damping element c_r . The blast load
138 is represented by a time series $p(t)$. The 2DOF configuration, represented in Fig. 3 (b), is used for verifying
139 the design methodology over a more realistic dynamics. In this representation, the cladding is connected to
140 the structure of mass m_s , connected to its based by a stiffness element k_s and a viscous element c_s .

Figure 3: (a) SDOF representation; and (b) 2DOF representation.

141 3.2. Blast load model

142 A typical blast pressure wave is shown in Fig.4 (a) [37]. At the beginning of the explosion, the air
 143 pressure builds up very rapidly to the peak reflected pressure value σ_{\max} . The pressure decays over time t_d
 144 (positive phase duration) and drops to the negative pressure σ_{\min} before dissipating over time t_n , (negative
 145 phase duration) for a total blast time duration $t_{\text{blast}} = t_d + t_n$. The positive phase ($t < t_d$) can be modeled
 146 using the general descending pulse model proposed by Li *et al.* [38] and the negative phase can be modeled
 147 by a bilinear function [39].

Figure 4: Time history curve for air blast wave pressure : (a) typical time history ; and (b) idealized time history.

148 In this study, the blast load is simplified using a linear approximation for the positive phase and neglecting
 149 the minimum pressure ($\sigma_{\min} \approx 0$ and $t_{\text{blast}} = t_d$). This idealized blast model is shown in Fig. 4 (b) in
 150 accordance with the current state of practice criteria documents for blast resistance [40]. The blast load $p(t)$

151 is taken as

$$p(t) = \begin{cases} F_m \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{blast}}}\right) & \text{if } 0 < t < t_{\text{blast}} \\ 0 & \text{if } t > t_{\text{blast}} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

152 where $F_m = A_c \sigma_{\text{max}}$ is the peak blast force, and A_c is the area of the cladding. The blast impulse I is taken
153 as

$$I = \int_0^{t_{\text{blast}}} p(t) dt = \frac{1}{2} F_m t_{\text{blast}} \quad (2)$$

154 For this study, it is assumed that the cladding will not fail under σ_{max} , with $\sigma_{\text{max}} \leq \sigma_{\text{cap}}$ where σ_{cap} is
155 the ultimate resistance of the cladding to avoid blowout failure. For example, government design criteria in
156 the United States require fenestration to resist pressures in the range 27.6-276 kPa (4-40 psi) depending on
157 the criteria document [41].

158 The plastic energy absorption of cladding panels has been previously studied. Ye and Ma [42] proposed a
159 load-cladding-structure model to investigate the mitigation performance of a foam cladding structure against
160 blast loads. The study demonstrated that the proposed foam cladding could absorb up to 60% of the blast
161 energy. Li *et al.* [43] conducted a finite element analysis to investigate the response of a six-story concrete
162 structure with exterior reinforced concrete (RC) cladding panels subjected to far-field blast loads. Results
163 showed that RC exterior cladding panels converted nearly 40% of the blast energy into the plastic strain
164 energy. Recently, Zhao *et al.* [44] proposed a foamed cement-based sacrificial cladding and investigated its
165 blast mitigation effect with varied cladding thickness by finite element analysis. The study demonstrated
166 that the peak stress of structure could be reduced by 10% and 20% using 6 cm and 8 cm-thickness foamed
167 cladding, respectively.

168 The focus of this study is on the transfer of blast-induced reactions from the cladding to the structure, not
169 the blast resistant design of the cladding itself. The nonlinear response of the individual cladding panels to
170 the blast load will be incorporated in future iterations of this procedure. The current approach is conservative
171 with regard to its intended focus because it assumes that all blast-induced forces are transferred through
172 the cladding-to-structure connections with no potential energy absorption or dissipation provided by the
173 plastic response or partial damage (such as cracking or shallow spalling) of the cladding. The nonlinear
174 cladding response is also commonly neglected in current practice when calculating the maximum base shear
175 experienced by buildings under blast loading [45, 46].

176 3.3. Impact rubber model

177 Several models have been developed for rubber impact bumpers, such as the linear impact spring, linear
178 viscoelastic impact [47], the Hertz model with nonlinear spring [48], and the Hertz model with nonlinear

179 damping models [49, 50, 51]. Here, the model presented by Polycarpou *et al.* [49] for a structural impact
 180 mitigation bumpers is selected. In this model, the resistive force of the impact rubber F_r is written:

$$F_r = \begin{cases} k_r u_r^n & \text{for } u_r < u_{r,\text{ult}} \quad \dot{u}_r > 0 \\ k_r u_{r,\text{ult}}^n + k_{r,y}(u_r - u_{r,\text{ult}}) & \text{for } u_r > u_{r,\text{ult}} \quad \dot{u}_r > 0 \\ k_r u_r^n (1 + c_r \dot{u}_r) & \text{for } \dot{u}_r < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

181 where u_r and $u_{r,\text{ult}}$ are the displacement and the ultimate compression capacity of the impact rubber,
 182 respectively; k_r and $k_{r,y}$ are the impact stiffness and the post-yield stiffness of the impact rubber, respectively;
 183 $n > 1$ is the impact exponent; and c_r is the impact rubber damping coefficient. The impact rubber stiffness
 184 k_r is taken as

$$k_r = \beta \frac{A_r k'_r}{l_r^n} \quad (4)$$

185 where β is a strain rate-dependent coefficient, A_r is the contact area of the impact rubber, and k'_r is the
 186 stiffness of the material. The value $\frac{A_r k'_r}{l_r^n}$ represents the static stiffness of the impact rubber. Reference [49]
 187 provides a semi-empirical equation to determine c_r .

$$c_r = \frac{3(1 - \text{COR}^2)}{2 \cdot \text{COR} \cdot \dot{u}_{\text{rubber}}} \quad (5)$$

188 where \dot{u}_{rubber} is impact velocity, and COR is the coefficient of restitution. Example values for all parameters
 189 can be found in Reference [49]. Fig. 5 shows the typical force-displacement ($F_r - u_r$) loop for the impact
 190 rubber based on that model.

Figure 5: Nonlinear rubber impact hysteresis.

191 4. Performance-Based Design Procedure

192 The proposed 3-step PBD procedure for the semi-active cladding connection system exposed to a blast
 193 load is illustrated in Fig. 6. Step 1 determines the design performance criteria, which include the maximum
 194 blast design pressure σ_{max} along with its period t_{blast} and the spacing l_c between the cladding and structure.
 195 The peak pressure and duration of blast can be obtained from the literature [40] based on the explosive

196 charge mass and the standoff distance. Step 2 consists of designing the dynamic parameters of the cladding
197 system, including m_c , c_c , k_c , and F_c , and obtaining the maximum displacement of the cladding $u_{c,\max}$ based
198 on transfer function H_1 to be compared with the performance parameter l_c from Step 1. If $u_{c,\max} \leq l_c$
199 the cladding will not collide with the structure, and the design of the impact rubber can be based on fail-
200 safe requirements if the cladding will also not collide with the rubber ($u_{c,\max} \leq (l_c - l_r)$). Otherwise, if
201 the cladding is to collide with any element, Step 3 is then used to design the impact rubber design. The
202 rubber thickness l_r will be designed in order to dissipate energy with a prescribed maximum compression of
203 $u_{r,\max}$, obtained through transfer functions H_2 and H_3 . If $u_{r,\max} \leq l_c$ is satisfied, then the design procedure
204 is finished. Otherwise, three design options could be considered: (1) change the allowable spacing l_c , (2)
205 change the dynamic parameters of the cladding system, or (3) iterate on the rubber thickness l_r . The
206 proposed PBD procedure is conducted using an SDOF system, and design parameter values will be selected
207 from analytical solutions. It is assumed that the peak dynamic response of cladding panel to blast will occur
208 at the first quarter cycle, and the dynamics of the structure can be assumed negligible during the maximum
209 cladding response (i.e. there will be a delay between the maximum response of the cladding and that of
210 the building due to high-speed load transfer). Although numerical solutions are more exact, the analytical
211 solution would allow designers to quickly select design parameters, therefore enabling a holistic integration
212 of the device within the structural design stage. Each step of the procedure is described in detail below.

213 *4.1. Step 1 : Performance criteria*

214 The first step is to establish parameters that will define the performance requirements of the cladding
215 system. These include the selection of the design blast load, and the allowable gap distance between the
216 cladding and structure l_c .

217 *4.1.1. Design blast pressure*

218 The design blast pressure can be selected based on three parameters: the explosive material, the explosive
219 charge weight W , and the standoff distance between the blast source and the target R . Most severe intentional
220 blast threats are vehicle-borne, and the mass of the explosive charge can be estimated based on quantities
221 of explosive that can be stored in various vehicles. Reference [52] provides estimated quantities of common
222 explosives based on vehicle types. To obtain the resulting blast pressure, the charge mass from different
223 explosive material is represented as an equivalent mass of TNT [53].

224 The standoff distance R can be based on several factors, including site security, roadway access, and
225 topography. The minimum standoff distance for inhabited buildings of conventional construction can be
226 directly obtained from Section 2.3.2.2.1 of ASCE/SEI 59-11 [54]. Based on the assumption that the explosive
227 consists of TNT, the following equation can be used to relate W and R to [the peak incident overpressure](#)

233 determined from Equation 9 [56]:

$$t_{\text{blast}} = W^{1/3} 10^{[-2.75 + 0.27 \log(Z)]} \quad (9)$$

234 *4.1.2. Allowable distance cladding-structure*

235 Typically, cladding panels are connected to the structure through hanger supports to resist gravity loads
 236 and tieback connections to resist lateral loads. The lateral connections require a minimum spacing $l_{c,\text{min}}$
 237 between the cladding panel and the structure for their installation, and can be as high as 6 in (15 cm) for
 238 prefabricated panels [57]. Allowances for rain drainage, mortar droppings, vapor diffusion, and fire/smoke
 239 spread prevention need to be taken into account as well. Free drainage occurs if the airspace is greater than
 240 3/8 in (1 cm) [58]. A minimum of 1 in (2.54 cm) airspace is needed to allow quick drying for the wall, thus
 241 impeding bacteria growth. For cast-in-place or site-installed cladding such as brick veneer, a minimum 2
 242 inch airspace is recommended to reduce the possibility that the mortar squeezes out into the air space during
 243 brick laying and makes permanent contact with the structure. In this study, it is assumed that the cladding
 244 is designed to avoid blowout under blast load; therefore, prefabricated cladding, which is generally more
 245 robust for lateral loads, is considered. Preliminary design of the spacing l_c needs to meet the aforementioned
 246 requirements with no less than the minimum gap spacing $l_{c,\text{min}}$.

247 *4.2. Step 2 : Dynamic parameters of cladding system*

248 The second step in the design is to select the dynamic parameters of the cladding system, including the
 249 friction capacity of the semi-active connection (used in passive mode). The equation of motion of an SDOF
 250 representation of the cladding system subjected to a blast load can be written

$$m_c \ddot{u}_c + c_c \dot{u}_c + k_c u_c + F_c = F_m \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{blast}}}\right) \quad \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq t_{\text{blast}} \quad (10a)$$

$$m_c \ddot{u}_c + c_c \dot{u}_c + k_c u_c + F_c = 0 \quad \text{for } t \geq t_{\text{blast}} \quad (10b)$$

251

252 with the friction force F_c is approximated using the Coulomb model:

$$F_c = f_c \text{sgn}(\dot{u}_c) \quad (11)$$

253 where f_c is the friction capacity of the cladding connection, and sgn is the sign or signum function:

$$\text{sgn}(\dot{u}_c) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } \dot{u}_c < 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \dot{u}_c = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } \dot{u}_c > 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

254 Because only the first quarter cycle of the response is considered, $F_c = f_c$. Eq. 10 can be used to
 255 characterize the dynamics of the cladding system before it collides with the impact rubber. Assuming that
 256 the first quarter cycle response time $T/4 \gg t_{\text{blast}}$, Eq. 10 (a) is solved to find the initial conditions for
 257 $u_c(t_{\text{blast}})$ and $\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{blast}})$ which are needed to solve Eq. 10 (b).

258 The solution of Eq. 10 (a) can be derived by Duhamels integral,

$$u_c(t) = \frac{1}{m\omega_d} \int_0^t \left[F_m \left(1 - \frac{\tau}{t_{\text{blast}}} \right) - f_c \right] e^{-\xi\omega_n(t-\tau)} \sin[\omega_d(t-\tau)] d\tau \quad (13)$$

259 where ξ , ω_n and ω_d are the damping ratio, natural frequency, and damped frequency of the cladding system,
 260 respectively. The final solution after integration by parts is expressed:

$$\begin{aligned} u_c(t) = & e^{-\xi\omega_n t} \left[\left(u_0 - \frac{f_c}{k_c} \right) \cos \omega_d t + \frac{\dot{u}_0 + \left(u_0 - \frac{f_c}{k_c} \right) \xi \omega_n}{\omega_d} \sin \omega_d t \right] + \frac{f_c}{k_c} \\ & + \frac{F_m}{k_c} \left[1 - e^{-\xi\omega_n t} \left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \sin \omega_d t + \cos \omega_d t \right) \right] \\ & - \frac{F_m}{k_c t_{\text{blast}}} \left[t - \frac{2\xi}{\omega_n} + \frac{e^{-\xi\omega_n t}}{\omega_n} \left(2\xi \cos \omega_d t + \frac{2\xi^2 - 1}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \sin \omega_d t \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

261 and

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{u}_c(t) = & e^{-\xi\omega_n t} \left[\dot{u}_0 \cos \omega_d t - \left(\frac{u_0 \omega_n - \frac{f_c}{k_c} \omega_n + \xi \dot{u}_0}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \right) \sin \omega_d t \right] + \frac{F_m e^{-\xi\omega_n t}}{k_c \sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \sin \omega_d t \\ & - \frac{F_m}{k_c t_{\text{blast}}} \left[1 - e^{-\xi\omega_n t} \left(\cos \omega_d t + \frac{\xi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \sin \omega_d t \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

262 where $0 \leq t \leq t_{\text{blast}}$. The solutions of Eq. 14 at $t = t_{\text{blast}}$ are used as initial condition for Eq. 10 (b). Eq.
 263 10 (b) can be solved using the summation of the homogenous solution and particular solution:

$$u_c(t) = e^{-\xi\omega_n(t-t_{\text{blast}})} \left[\left(u_c(t_{\text{blast}}) - \frac{f_c}{k_c} \right) \cos \omega_d(t-t_{\text{blast}}) + \frac{\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{blast}}) + \left(u_c(t_{\text{blast}}) - \frac{f_c}{k_c} \right) \xi \omega_n}{\omega_d} \sin \omega_d(t-t_{\text{blast}}) \right] + \frac{f_c}{k_c} \quad (16)$$

264 where $t > t_{\text{blast}}$. Eq. 16 is used to find the maximum displacement, which occurs at time t_1 . Taking the
 265 derivative of Eq. 16 equal to zero, and the result of t in first cycle can infer to the maximum u_c , $u_{c,\text{max}}$.

$$t_1 = \frac{\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{blast}}) \sqrt{1-\xi^2}}{\left(u_c(t_{\text{blast}}) - \frac{f_c}{k_c} \right) \omega_n + \xi \dot{u}_c(t_{\text{blast}})} \right)}{\omega_d} + t_{\text{blast}} \quad (17)$$

$$u_{c,\max} = e^{-\xi\omega_n(t_1-t_{\text{blast}})} \frac{\sqrt{\left(u_c(t_{\text{blast}}) - \frac{f_c}{k_c}\right)^2 \omega_d^2 + \left(\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{blast}}) + \left(u_c(t_{\text{blast}}) - \frac{f_c}{k_c}\right) \xi\omega_n\right)^2}}{\omega_d} + \frac{f_c}{k_c} \quad (18)$$

266 A dimensionless transfer function H_1 is then created to facilitate the design procedure:

$$H_1 = \frac{u_{c,\max}}{\frac{F_m}{k_c}} = \frac{u_{c,\max}}{u_{\text{st}}} \quad (19)$$

267 where $u_{\text{st}} = \frac{F_m}{k_c}$ is the static displacement from a constant peak blast force F_m .

268 The maximum displacement of cladding $u_{c,\max}$ can be obtained from Eq. 19 or from the H_1 plots as
 269 demonstrated later in Section 5 (Numerical Simulations). The maximum displacement is used to verify if
 270 $u_{c,\max} \leq l_c$. If so, an impact rubber bumper with minimum thickness can be designed, and a second check
 271 can be conducted to ensure that $u_{c,\max} \leq (l_c - l_r)$. Otherwise, the impact rubber needs to be carefully
 272 designed under Step 3.

273 4.3. Step 3: Parameters of impact rubber

274 An impact rubber of length l_r (Fig. 3 (a)) is used to prevent the cladding system from colliding with the
 275 structure. Step 3 consists of sizing this rubber bumper. The design process starts with a second transfer
 276 function H_2

$$H_2 = \frac{I_{\text{structure}}}{I_{\text{blast}}} = \frac{m_c \dot{u}_{\text{rubber}}}{\frac{1}{2} F_m t_{\text{blast}}} \quad (20)$$

277 where \dot{u}_{rubber} is the solution of the time derivative of Eq. 18 for $t = t_{\text{rubber}}$, which represents the time of
 278 impact with the impact bumper, I_{blast} is the impulse of the initial blast and $I_{\text{structure}}$ is the momentum of
 279 the cladding when it hits the rubber. The impact velocity of the cladding can be calculated using Eq. 18,
 280 which in turn will be used calculating the maximum deformation of the rubber.

281 To obtain the analytical solution of maximum rubber deformation, the rubber model is represented as a
 282 linear stiffness element to provide a more convenient mathematical form [2]. The mass of the rubber bumper
 283 is neglected, and the bumper will only provide additional resistant force when impacted by the cladding
 284 panel. Note that although a linear stiffness element cannot dissipate energy during a full cycle of harmonic
 285 motion, it can still be used to represent the rubber dynamics since only the gap-closing phase is considered.
 286 To do so, the hysteresis of the impact rubber (Fig. 5) can be compared to the hysteresis of a linear stiffness
 287 element in the approaching phase. The impact rubber is approximated using

$$F_r = k_{\text{eq}} u_r \quad (21)$$

288 where F_r is the damping force, k_{eq} is the linear stiffness coefficient, and u_r is the deformation of the impact
 289 rubber. Assuming a periodic excitation, the response of the equivalent system is written:

$$u_r(t) = \bar{u}_r \sin(\omega t) \quad (22)$$

290 where \bar{u}_r is the amplitude of periodic excitation. To avoid the case of exceeding the ultimate compression
 291 capacity $u_{r,\text{ult}}$ in Fig. 5, \bar{u}_r is assumed to be half of the thickness of impact rubber due to $u_{r,\text{ult}} = 80\%l_r$
 292 reported in Reference [49]. Eq. 21 becomes

$$F_r = k_{\text{eq}} \bar{u}_r \sin(\omega t) \quad (23)$$

293 The energy dissipation of the impact rubber W_r for this quarter cycle response using this equivalent
 294 energy dissipation representation is expressed

$$\begin{aligned} W_r &= \int_0^{\bar{u}_r} k_{\text{eq}} u_r du_r \\ &= \frac{1}{2} k_{\text{eq}} \bar{u}_r^2 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

295 In addition, the energy dissipation of the impact rubber can be taken as the area under the gap-closing
 296 phase curve. From Eq. 3, F_r^A represents the impact force when cladding is in the gap-closing phase, and
 297 F_r^R represents the force in restitution phase. To simplify the integration, an integer value is used for the
 298 exponent. Neglecting the post yield phase of impact rubber, the energy dissipation in the approaching phase
 299 can be computed using Polycarpou's dynamic model for rubber (Eq. 3):

$$\begin{aligned} W_r &= \int_0^{\bar{u}_r} F_r^A du_c \\ &= \int_0^{\bar{u}_r} k_r u_r^{2.65} du_r \\ &= \frac{1}{3.65} k_r \bar{u}_r^{3.65} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

300 Equating Eq. 24 and Eq. 25 gives

$$k_{\text{eq}} = \frac{2k_r \bar{u}_r^{1.65}}{3.65} \quad (26)$$

Figure 7: Equivalent linear stiffness hysteresis.

301 The equivalent energy dissipation concept is illustrated in Fig. 7. The red triangle area represents energy
 302 dissipation from the linear stiffness element and the gray shaded area represents the energy dissipation from
 303 the impact rubber, where both areas are equal. Eq. 10 (b) is modified to include the dynamics of the impact
 304 rubber using the equivalent stiffness concept:

$$m\ddot{u}_c(t) + c\dot{u}_c(t) + (k + k_{\text{eq}})u_c(t) = -f_c \quad (27)$$

305 where $t > t_{\text{rubber}}$. The rubber deformation follows the cladding displacement from the point where $u_c =$
 306 $u_{c,\text{max}}$. The analytical solution for the rubber deformation is similar to Eq. 16, but with $k_{\text{new}} = k_{\text{eq}} + k_c$,
 307 where ξ_r and ω_{dr} are the modified damping ratio and damped frequency.

$$u_r(t) = e^{-\xi_r \omega_{\text{dr}}(t-t_{\text{rubber}})} \left[-\frac{f_c + k_c u_c(t_{\text{rubber}})}{k_{\text{new}}} \cos \omega_{\text{dr}}(t-t_{\text{rubber}}) \right] \\ + e^{-\xi_r \omega_{\text{dr}}(t-t_{\text{rubber}})} \left[\frac{\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{rubber}})k_{\text{new}} - (f_c + k_c u_c(t_{\text{rubber}}))\xi_r \omega_r}{k_{\text{new}}\omega_{\text{dr}}} \sin \omega_{\text{dr}}(t-t_{\text{rubber}}) \right] + \frac{f_c + k_c u_c(t_{\text{rubber}})}{k_{\text{new}}} \quad (28)$$

308 where $u_c(t_{\text{rubber}}) = l_c - l_r$ is the space between the cladding element and the impact rubber. Using the
 309 analytical solution from Eq. 28 and the time of maximum deformation $u_{r,\text{max}}$, a third transfer function H_3
 310 is obtained:

$$t_2 = \frac{\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{rubber}})k_{\text{new}}\sqrt{1-\xi_r^2}}{-f_c\omega_r - k_c u_c(t_{\text{rubber}})\omega_r + \xi_r k_{\text{new}}\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{rubber}})} \right)}{\omega_{\text{dr}}} + t_{\text{rubber}} \quad (29)$$

$$u_{r,\text{max}} = e^{-\xi_r \omega_{\text{dr}}(t_2-t_{\text{rubber}})} \frac{\sqrt{(u_c(t_{\text{rubber}})k_c + f_c)^2 \omega_{\text{dr}}^2 + (\dot{u}_c(t_{\text{rubber}})k_{\text{new}} - (u_c(t_{\text{rubber}})k_c + f_c)\xi_r \omega_r)^2}}{\omega_{\text{dr}} k_{\text{new}}} + \frac{f_c + k_c u_c(t_{\text{rubber}})}{k_{\text{new}}} \quad (30)$$

$$H_3 = \frac{u_{r,\text{max}}}{u_{\text{st}}} \quad (31)$$

311 where $u_{\text{st}} = \frac{F_m}{k_c}$ is the static deformation. Transfer function H_3 provides the deformation of the impact
312 rubber based on the design parameters selected under Steps 1 and 2, with the objective to obtain a rubber
313 deformation smaller than its design thickness l_r . Otherwise, other design parameters need to be selected
314 and the PBD procedure be iterated, as explained earlier.

315 5. Numerical Simulations

316 In this section, numerical simulations are conducted to verify the proposed PBD methodology. Simu-
317 lations are based on a 1:4 scale six-story three-bay structure equipped with cladding panels spanning each
318 floor. This structure was selected due to the availability of parameters and results found in the literature
319 [3, 57], in which the authors studied an advanced passive energy-dissipating cladding connector for seis-
320 mic design. Here, we used the cladding panel material consistent with [57], and replaced the connector by
321 the proposed semi-active connection. Each cladding panel is attached to the structure using two tie back
322 connectors and two bearing supports. The semi-active connection is installed as a replacement to tie back
323 connectors, and only the bearing connectors are assumed to provide lateral stiffness and inherent damping
324 between the cladding and the structure (k_c and c_c , respectively).

Figure 8: Simulated structure with cladding panels.

327 The 18DOF representation is illustrated in Fig. 8, which contains one translational DOF per floor, and
 328 two translational DOF per connection between the cladding and structure. Each cladding panel is modeled
 329 as a rigid bar of mass m_c and has two degree of freedoms at either end connected to the structure. Again,
 330 the nonlinear response of the cladding will be considered in future work, and the assumption of a rigid bar
 331 is consistent with current approaches for conservatively calculating the base shear and cladding-to-structure
 332 load transfer for buildings under blast loading [45, 46]. The first cladding element spanning between ground
 333 level and the first floor has its lower semi-active connection directly attached to the ground. Details of the
 334 cladding connections are schematized in Fig. 3 (a). The dynamic properties of the structure and cladding
 335 elements are listed in Table 1, based on the properties provided in Reference [57].

Table 1: Dynamic properties of cladding structure [57]

floor	mass (kg)	stiffness (kN/m)	damping (kN·s/m)	cladding mass (kg)
6	3175	3000	16.32	450
5	3175	3000	16.32	450
4	3175	3000	16.32	450
3	3175	3000	16.32	450
2	3175	3000	16.32	450
1	3175	3000	16.32	450

336 The equation of motion for the 18DOF system has the form

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{E}_p\mathbf{P} + \mathbf{E}_f\mathbf{F} \quad (32)$$

337 where $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{18 \times 1}$ is the displacement vector, $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{12 \times 1}$ is the blast loading input vector, $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{12 \times 1}$ is the
338 control force vector including the friction force and rubber damping force, $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{18 \times 18}$, $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{18 \times 18}$, $\mathbf{K} \in$
339 $\mathbb{R}^{18 \times 18}$ are the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices, respectively, and $\mathbf{E}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{18 \times 12}$, and $\mathbf{E}_f \in \mathbb{R}^{18 \times 12}$ are
340 the blast loading and control input location matrices, respectively.

341 The state-space representation of Eq. (32) is given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{U} + \mathbf{B}_p\mathbf{P} + \mathbf{B}_f\mathbf{F} \quad (33)$$

342 where $\mathbf{U} = [\mathbf{u} \quad \dot{\mathbf{u}}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{36 \times 1}$ is state vector and

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{K} & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{C} \end{bmatrix}_{36 \times 36} \quad \mathbf{B}_p = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{E}_p \end{bmatrix}_{36 \times 12} \quad \mathbf{B}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{E}_f \end{bmatrix}_{36 \times 12}$$

343 where \mathbf{I} is an 18×18 identity matrix.

Table 2: Comparison of modal properties

mode	reported [57] (Hz)	model (Hz)	difference (%)	model Γ (%)
first	1.17	1.17	0.00	86.96
second	3.88	3.47	-10.57	8.91

344 Table 2 compares modal parameters between the values reported in [57] and the ones from the 18DOF
345 model. The first mode of the model matches the first mode of the six-story building, and the modal
346 participation factor Γ shows that the first mode largely dominates the response of the 18DOF representation.
347 Two design blast loads are considered for this study. The first is based on a 500-kg mass of TNT (approximate
348 explosive mass in a closed van delivery method [52]) at a standoff distance of 25 m. This load will be used in
349 Sections 5.2 and 5.3 to compare the proposed analytical solution with the numerical results and demonstrate
350 the PBD procedure. A smaller charge weight of 100-kg of TNT (approximate explosive mass in a compact
351 car trunk delivery method [52]) at the same 25-m standoff will be introduced in Section 5.4 to evaluate the
352 performance of the proposed model and procedure for a more moderate blast load. There is a greater potential
353 for nonlinear cladding response due to the 500-kg charge than the 100-kg charge, and comparing their effects
354 will evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed connections for a range of blast reaction magnitudes.

355 The amplitude of blast load F_m for both charge weights are calculated using Eq.7 based on the maximum
356 blast pressure σ_{\max} and a total cladding panel area A_c of 3.33 m² at each floor. Parameter values of the
357 500-kg design blast load for each nodes are listed in Table 3 (values for the 100-kg charge will be provided
358 later in Section 5.4). The resulting values σ_{\max} are within a typical range σ_{cap} as discussed in Section 3.2.
359 The pressure is taken as a constant between two half floors, resulting in the blast load equal for adjacent
360 connections ($p_4 = p_5$ in Fig. 8, for instance).

Table 3: Design blast load (500-kg TNT) for 18DOF system

node	R (m)	Z (m/kg ^{1/3})	σ_{\max} (kPa)	F_m (kN)	t_{blast} (ms)
u_7	25.00	3.15	224.00	370.67	24
u_8	25.27	3.18	218.05	359.78	24
u_9	25.27	3.18	218.05	359.78	24
u_{10}	26.05	3.28	200.25	330.42	25
u_{11}	26.05	3.28	200.25	330.42	25
u_{12}	27.30	3.44	176.03	290.45	25
u_{13}	27.30	3.44	176.03	290.45	25
u_{14}	28.97	3.65	150.29	247.98	25
u_{15}	28.97	3.65	150.29	247.98	25
u_{16}	30.98	3.90	126.37	208.50	26
u_{17}	30.98	3.90	126.37	208.50	26
u_{18}	33.27	4.18	105.79	174.56	26

361 *5.1.2. 2DOF system*

362 The six story structure is also modeled as 2DOF system by lumping the six structural mass elements m_s
 363 into a single mass (1DOF) and the six cladding mass elements m_c into a single cladding element to obtain
 364 a representation similar to the one schematized in Fig. 3 (b). A structural damping ratio of 2% is assumed.
 365 A simplified triangular blast load is used for the simulations ($p(t)$) using blast load parameters calculated
 366 following the approach described in Section 4.1.1. The peak design blast load F_m used in 2DOF system
 367 is summation of blast peak load in 18DOF system. Note that this 2DOF system assumption is only used
 368 for verifying the SDOF approximation and it does not necessarily represent the dynamic of 18DOF system.
 369 The resulting parameters used for the numerical simulation are listed in Table 4. Remark that a different
 370 value for k_c than the one used in Reference [57] to obtain a more compliant connection to improve energy
 371 mitigation.

Table 4: Model parameters for 2DOF representation

	parameter	value	unit
system	m_s	19051	kg
	k_s	1029	kN/m
	c_s	56	kN·s/m
	m_c	2700	kg
blast	W	500	kg
	R	25	m
	Z	2.5	m/kg ^{1/3}
	σ_{\max}	218	kPa
	F_m	3419	kN
	t_{blast}	24	ms

372 *5.2. Verification of the SDOF approximation*

373 Before conducting simulations of the 18DOF system, the PBD methodology is first verified for the 2DOF
 374 representation of the building to demonstrate the assumption that cladding can be designed based on an
 375 SDOF approximation. The validity of the assumption is investigated through the comparison of transfer
 376 function plots obtained from the PBD procedure and from numerical simulations. In what follows, the PBD
 377 transfer functions H_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are compared against the transfer functions of the 2DOF H_i^* obtained
 378 numerically, using a performance metric \tilde{H}_i :

$$\tilde{H}_i = \frac{H_i - H_i^*}{H_i^*} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (34)$$

379 First, H_1 and H_1^* transfer functions are plotted as functions of the blast duration ratio t_{blast}/T_n for
 380 different friction capacity ratios f_c/F_m in Fig. 9 (a), over the range 0.1% to 3.0%. The performance metric
 381 \tilde{H}_1 is plotted in Fig. 9 (b). The error in H_1 is larger for small ratios t_{blast}/T_n , and converges to 0 with
 382 increasing t_{blast}/T_n . The magnitude of the error increases with increasing friction ratio. Generally, the error
 383 is positive, which results in an over-estimation of the cladding displacement. The error is negative for a zero
 384 friction ratio ($f_c/F_m = 0\%$), because the blast energy will be transmitted to the structure (no dissipation)
 385 and the model will underestimate cladding displacement due to the unmodeled displacement of the structure.

Figure 9: H_1 function for $\xi = 2\%$: (a) H_1 and H_1^* ; and (b) \tilde{H}_1 .

386 Second, transfer function H_2 is verified through the investigation of its fitting performance index \tilde{H}_2 over
 387 different values of relative rubber thickness $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st}$. Plots are shown in Figs. 10 and 11 for the ratio
 388 range 1% to 4%, which represents a large range of spacing $l_c - l_r$ as u_{st} is relatively large under blast load. A
 389 null value for H_2 signifies that the cladding does not collide with the structure. The error \tilde{H}_2 is high for H_2
 390 close to 0, and increases with increasing relative rubber thicknesses. The error is also higher for increasing
 391 friction ratio. In both cases, this high level of error is due to increasing nonlinearities that are not captured
 392 by the analytical solutions. However, the error is positive in all cases, which signifies that the cladding will
 393 be over-designed therefore provide additional safety. Also, the error converges to zero with increasing blast
 394 duration ratio.

Figure 10: H_2 function for $\xi = 2\%$ and $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 1\%$: (a) H_2 and H_2^* ; and (b) \tilde{H}_2 .

Figure 11: H_2 function for $\xi = 2\%$ and $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 4\%$: (a) H_2 and H_2^* ; and (b) \tilde{H}_2 .

395 Third, the H_3 function is plotted under different friction capacity ratios f_c/F_m , relative rubber thickness
 396 ratios $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st}$ and impact rubber stiffness ratios k_c/k_r in Figs. 12 to 15. The error \tilde{H}_3 is high when
 397 rubber has smaller deformations (H_3 close to 0). As t_{blast}/T_n increases, the error \tilde{H}_3 quickly decreases to
 398 reach a negative value for a higher relative rubber stiffness or lower ratio k_c/k_r .

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: H_3 function for $\xi = 2\%$, $f_c/F_m = 1\%$, and $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 1\%$: (a) H_3 and H_3^* ; and (b) \dot{H}_3 .

(a)

(b)

Figure 13: H_3 function for $\xi = 2\%$, $f_c/F_m = 1\%$, and $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 4\%$: (a) H_3 and H_3^* ; and (b) \dot{H}_3 .

Figure 14: H_3 function for $\xi = 2\%$, $f_c/F_m = 3\%$, and $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 1\%$: (a) H_3 and H_3^* ; and (b) \dot{H}_3 .

Figure 15: H_3 function for $\xi = 2\%$, $f_c/F_m = 3\%$, and $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 4\%$: (a) H_3 and H_3^* ; and (b) \dot{H}_3 .

399 5.3. Demonstration of PBD procedure

400 In this section, the proposed PBD procedure is demonstrated using the six-story structure shown in Fig.
 401 8. Recall that, similar to Section 5.2, the 500-kg charge size is used to make this comparison. The dynamic
 402 parameters of the cladding system and impact rubber, at each floor, are designed based on the PBD transfer
 403 function results H_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) obtained in the previous section for an SDOF system.

404 Step 1: Performance Criteria

405 The design blast load parameters F_m and t_{blast} for each node are taken from Table 3. The spacing l_c at
 406 each floor is set to 0.4 m for the preliminary design, based on the minimum requirements reviewed in Section
 407 4.1.2.

408 **Step 2: Dynamic Parameters of Cladding System**

409 The mass of each cladding panel m_c is taken as fixed, as provided in Reference [57]. Using the H_1 plot
 410 (Fig. 9 (a)) with the assumption of a cladding damping ratio $\xi = 2\%$, a blast duration ratio $t_{\text{blast}}/T_n = 3\%$
 411 with a friction capacity ratio $f_c/F_m = 1\%$ yields $H_1 = 0.081$. This H_1 value is used to compute $u_{c,\text{max}}$ at each
 412 floor using Equation 19. Table 5 lists the results for each node, as well as k_c and c_c to obtain $t_{\text{blast}}/T_n = 3\%$
 413 and $\xi = 2\%$. With these design parameters, all of the nodes exceed the allowable deformation of 0.4 m,
 414 necessitating design step 3 for appropriate sizing of the impact rubber.

Table 5: Cladding connection design parameters from Step 2

node	m_c (kg)	T_n (s)	k_c (kN/m)	c_c (kN·s/m)	f_c (kN)	u_{st} (m)	$u_{c,\text{max}}$ (m)
u_7	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	3.71	27.27	2.21
u_8	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	3.60	26.62	2.16
u_9	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	3.60	26.62	2.16
u_{10}	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	3.30	24.85	2.01
u_{11}	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	3.30	24.85	2.01
u_{12}	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	2.90	22.40	1.81
u_{13}	225	0.76	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	2.90	22.40	1.81
u_{14}	225	0.8	15.11	7.38×10^{-2}	2.48	19.74	1.60
u_{15}	225	0.8	13.88	7.07×10^{-2}	2.48	19.74	1.60
u_{16}	225	0.8	13.88	7.07×10^{-2}	2.09	17.21	1.40
u_{17}	225	0.8	13.88	7.07×10^{-2}	2.09	17.21	1.40
u_{18}	225	0.8	13.88	7.07×10^{-2}	1.75	14.97	1.21

415 **Step 3: Parameters of Impact Rubber**

416 For simplicity, both the cladding-structure spacing $l_c = 0.4$ m and the rubber thickness l_r are assumed
 417 constant throughout the height of the structure. The design of l_r is based on the blast load at the first floor,
 418 which represents the worst case scenario. An initial rubber thickness is selected taking $(l_c - l_r)/u_{st} = 1\%$
 419 and yielding $l_r = 0.12$ m. The ultimate compression capacity is $u_{r,\text{ult}} = 0.8l_r = 0.096$ m. The value $H_2 = 0.96$
 420 is obtained from the H_2 plot (Fig. 10 (a)) using the design parameters from Step 2 ($t_{\text{blast}}/T_n = 3\%$,
 421 $f_c/F_m = 1\%$), which results in $u_{c,\text{max}} = 2.21$ m. This value is much higher than the cladding-structure
 422 spacing l_c . Therefore, H_3 must be obtained such that $H_3 \leq u_{r,\text{ult}}/u_{st} = 0.053$. Using H_3 from Fig. 12 (a), a
 423 value of $k_c/k_r = 0.001\%$ would satisfy this requirement, with $H_3 = 0.0025$. The resulting maximum rubber
 424 deflection is $u_{r,\text{max}} = 0.068$ m. Since the maximum deformation of rubber $u_{r,\text{max}}$ is smaller than the rubber's
 425 design thickness l_r , the design is completed. A detailed design of the impact rubbers can be conducted using
 426 Equation 4 with rubber properties found in Reference [49].

427 5.4. Simulation results

428 The 18DOF model is first verified under a design blast excitation of a 500-kg charge. The discrete form
 429 of a Duhamel integral is used to numerically simulate Eq. (33) [2]:

$$\mathbf{U}(t + 1) = e^{\mathbf{A}\Delta t}\mathbf{U}(t) + \mathbf{A}^{-1}(e^{\mathbf{A}\Delta t} - \mathbf{I})[\mathbf{B}_f\mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}_p\mathbf{P}(t)] \quad (35)$$

430 where Δt is the time interval used in the simulation, taken as 0.0001s. Fig. 16 is a plot of the maximum
 431 cladding and rubber displacement results. The maximum rubber and cladding deformations at each node
 432 are compared with design values $l_c = 0.4\text{m}$ and $l_r = 0.12\text{m}$. Maximum deformation of rubber reduce from first
 433 floor (node 8) to top floor (node 18) caused from decreasing peak blast load. All deformations are smaller
 434 than design values, demonstrating that the proposed PBD procedure from an SDOF system provides an
 435 adequate design methodology for an MDOF system.

Figure 16: Maximum deformation of cladding and rubber.

436 The performance of proposed connection (“controlled” case) at mitigating inter-story drift and accel-
 437 eration is also evaluated versus a cladding system attached with conventional connections (“uncontrolled”
 438 case), where k_c is assumed to be infinitely stiff and no lateral stiffness is provided by the cladding [57]. A
 439 comparison of the time series inter-story displacements at the first and top floors under design blast load
 440 are plotted in Figs. 17 and 18, as well as the corresponding rubber peak deformations. Results demonstrate
 441 that proposed cladding system provides great mitigation performance under significant blast excitation. The
 442 peak deformation of the rubber impact bumpers is larger at the first impact, as expected.

Figure 17: (a) Comparison of displacement response at first floor; (b) peak rubber deformation at node 8 (zoom on 0.5s).

Figure 18: (a) Comparison of displacement response at top floor; (b) peak rubber deformation at node 18 (zoom on 0.5s).

443 To evaluate the relative effectiveness of the proposed connection under more moderate blast loads (for
 444 which nonlinear cladding response may realistically be less likely), additional simulations of the 18DOF
 445 numerical model are conducted using the blast loads due to the 100-kg charge mass of TNT. Parameter
 446 values of this excitation are calculated based on Section 4.1.1 and are listed in Table 6.

Table 6: Simulated blast load (100-kg TNT) for 18DOF system

node	R (m)	Z (m/kg ^{1/3})	σ_{\max} (kPa)	F_m (kN)	t_{blast} (ms)
u_7	25.00	5.39	59.49	98.16	28
u_8	25.27	5.44	58.20	96.03	28
u_9	25.27	5.44	58.20	96.03	28
u_{10}	26.05	5.61	54.67	90.21	28
u_{11}	26.05	5.61	54.67	90.21	28
u_{12}	27.30	5.88	49.75	82.09	29
u_{13}	27.30	5.88	49.75	82.09	29
u_{14}	28.97	6.23	44.35	73.18	29
u_{15}	28.97	6.23	44.35	73.18	29
u_{16}	30.98	6.66	39.11	64.54	30
u_{17}	30.98	6.66	39.11	64.54	30
u_{18}	33.27	7.15	34.40	56.75	30

447 The maximum inter-story drift and acceleration reductions at each floor resulting from the controlled case
 448 under various blast excitations are compared and listed in Table 7. The cladding system under 100-kg TNT
 449 provides higher inter-story reduction values than the 500-kg case below the third floor due to lower peak blast
 450 load values. Above the third floor, the 500-kg case demonstrates better inter-story drift mitigation since no
 451 rubber-cladding collision and energy dissipation from impact rubber occur for the 100-kg case. Under both
 452 blast load scenarios, the decrease of inter-story drift reduction from the first to the third floor are caused by
 453 a reduced cladding stiffness and friction capacity (Table 5). Above the third floor, the performance increases
 454 as the peak blast load magnitude rapidly decreases with increasing diagonal standoff. Comparing the overall
 455 acceleration mitigation shows that the designed cladding system can provide significant improvement for
 456 different severities of blast excitations. The high acceleration reduction is caused by the absorption of the
 457 blast reaction at the cladding level.

Table 7: Maximum response reduction

floor	500-kg TNT		100-kg TNT	
	inter-story drift (%)	acceleration (%)	inter-story drift (%)	acceleration (%)
1	28.32	90.93	30.20	89.93
2	26.91	87.19	32.83	86.43
3	31.22	88.54	45.93	88.06
4	47.27	78.42	40.65	82.64
5	58.79	84.81	43.38	85.31
6	67.67	71.68	38.93	79.80

458 6. Conclusions

459 Explosive materials deliver large shock-wave pressures to nearby structures and can cause significant
460 damage in a very short duration. Typically, cladding systems for buildings are connected to the structure
461 using connections with very high stiffness, which provide direct transfer of blast-induced reactions to the
462 structural system. In this paper, a novel semi-active cladding connection is proposed for mitigating this
463 high-rate load transfer. Instead of simply providing rigid lateral support for cladding, this new mechanism
464 is an active participant in energy dissipation under blast load. A semi-active friction mechanism is used to
465 provide a variable damping force, and an impact rubber bumper is utilized to absorb pounding energy for
466 large connection displacements.

467 A performance-based procedure has been proposed for the design of this new cladding connection. It
468 contains three steps: (1) blast load design, (2) cladding and friction device design, and (3) impact rubber
469 design. Three dimensionless transfer functions were derived using an equivalent SDOF system. These func-
470 tions allow rapid preliminary design of the cladding system and have been verified by numerical simulation
471 of the 2DOF system. Results show that the PBD procedure offers adequate design values with positive
472 performance metrics in most cases. It is computationally convenient and reasonably accurate to implement
473 the design value from the SDOF system for the MDOF system. Negative error values may arise in the design
474 of the rubber bumper for a limited range of scenarios, but this can be accommodated by recommending a
475 slightly larger design thickness value to provide additional safety.

476 Furthermore, the proposed cladding connection was designed and simulated in a six story structure as
477 an example for the proposed PBD procedure. A 18DOF system is used as a prototype, and the blast-
478 induced performance of the structure with the proposed friction-based connections is compared with that
479 using conventional cladding connections. Numerical simulation results show that the proposed cladding
480 connection offers significant reductions of blast-induced story displacements and accelerations. Moreover,

481 the simulation results show that the largest rubber deformation occurs in the first cladding impact cycle,
482 which supports the assumptions inherent in models associated with the PBD approach. The results of this
483 study indicate that this new semi-active cladding system shows promise for practical considerations of blast
484 mitigation for buildings.

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